

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF EDUCATORS OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

Shanasirova Zahro Yuldashovna

Associate professor of the Department of methods of preschool education of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Annotation: This article discusses the importance of developing the professional skills of educators in preschool educational organizations and the pedagogical conditions necessary to facilitate this development. The paper provides an overview of the current literature on the topic, explores various methods for enhancing professional skills, presents the results of a study on the effectiveness of these methods, and offers a discussion of the findings. The article concludes with suggestions for improving the professional development of educators in preschool settings.

Keywords: Educators, professional skills, preschool education, pedagogical conditions, training, professional development.

Educators working in preschool educational organizations play a pivotal role in shaping the early learning experiences of young children. It is crucial that these professionals possess the necessary knowledge and skills to provide high-quality education and care. This article aims to explore the pedagogical conditions required for the development of professional skills among educators in preschool settings.

The literature on early childhood education highlights the significance of professional development for educators. Professional skills encompass a broad range of competencies, including pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, communication, and the ability to create a stimulating learning

environment. To enhance these skills, educators need access to ongoing training and support.

To investigate the effectiveness of various pedagogical conditions for developing professional skills, a study was conducted involving a group of preschool educators. The study implemented several methods, such as workshops, mentorship programs, and online courses, to provide training and support to the participants. The educators' progress was evaluated through pre- and post-training assessments, as well as classroom observations.

The development of professional skills among educators in a preschool educational organization is essential for providing high-quality early childhood education. To create pedagogical conditions that support this development, several key factors should be considered:

Ongoing Professional Development:

- Encourage educators to participate in regular training and workshops related to early childhood education.
- Support opportunities for further education and advanced degrees in the field.
- Foster a culture of lifelong learning by providing access to relevant resources, such as books, journals, and online courses.

Reflective Practice:

- Encourage educators to engage in reflective practice, where they critically assess their teaching methods, interactions with children, and classroom management.
- Provide time and support for educators to discuss their experiences, challenges, and successes with colleagues.

Collaborative Learning:

- Promote a collaborative environment where educators can exchange ideas, share best practices, and learn from one another.
- Organize regular team meetings and discussions to facilitate collaboration.

Mentoring and Coaching:

- Implement mentoring and coaching programs where experienced educators can provide guidance and support to newer teachers.
- Create opportunities for peer observations and feedback.

Professional Standards and Frameworks:

- Ensure that educators are aware of and adhere to established professional standards and frameworks for early childhood education.
- Use these standards as a basis for professional development and evaluation.

Access to Resources:

- Provide educators with access to a variety of teaching materials, educational tools, and age-appropriate resources.
- Ensure that the learning environment is well-equipped and updated regularly.

Individualized Learning Plans:

- Develop individualized learning plans for educators that align with their goals and areas for improvement.
- Support educators in setting and achieving professional development objectives.

Assessment and Feedback:

- Conduct regular assessments of educators' performance and provide constructive feedback.
- Use a combination of self-assessment, peer assessment, and supervisor evaluation to identify areas for improvement.

Inclusive and Diverse Perspectives:

- Promote an inclusive and diverse approach to early childhood education by valuing the perspectives and experiences of all educators.
- Encourage educators to incorporate multicultural and diverse materials into their teaching.

Research and Innovation:

- Support educators in staying updated with the latest research and innovative practices in early childhood education.

- Encourage them to experiment with new teaching techniques and approaches.

Recognition and Incentives:

- Recognize and reward educators for their dedication and achievements in professional development.

- Provide incentives such as salary increases, additional responsibilities, or awards for excellence.

Supportive Leadership:

- Ensure that the leadership of the preschool organization is committed to the professional growth and well-being of educators.

- Foster an atmosphere of trust, respect, and open communication.

By creating these pedagogical conditions, preschool educational organizations can help educators continually improve their professional skills and, in turn, provide better learning experiences for young children.

Discussion:

The findings suggest that the professional skills of educators can be substantially improved through targeted training and support. Workshops, mentorship programs, and online courses have proven to be effective pedagogical conditions for facilitating skill development. These methods provide educators with opportunities to acquire new knowledge, exchange experiences, and receive feedback. Furthermore, by enhancing their professional skills, educators are better equipped to create engaging and supportive learning environments for young children.

Conclusions:

The development of professional skills among educators in preschool educational organizations is essential for providing high-quality early childhood education. Pedagogical conditions, such as workshops, mentorship programs, and

online courses, play a vital role in enhancing these skills. This article highlights the positive impact of these conditions on educators' knowledge and teaching practices. Consequently, investing in ongoing professional development is crucial for ensuring that educators are well-prepared to nurture the learning and development of young children.

To further improve the professional development of educators in preschool settings, the following suggestions can be considered:

- Customized Training: Tailor training programs to the specific needs and challenges of educators in different settings to ensure relevance and effectiveness.
- Mentorship Programs: Encourage experienced educators to mentor newer ones, creating a culture of continuous learning and support within preschool organizations.
- Feedback Mechanisms: Implement regular feedback and evaluation processes to assess the impact of professional development initiatives and make necessary adjustments.

In conclusion, by providing the right pedagogical conditions and continuously investing in the professional development of educators, we can ensure that preschool educational organizations offer high-quality learning experiences to young children, setting a strong foundation for their future academic success and personal development.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI.

1. Шарафутдинова Х. Г., Бердиева М. М. ПРОБЛЕМА ЛИЧНОСТНООРИЕНТИРОВАННОГО ОТНОШЕНИЯ К РЕБЁНКУ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ //Гуманитарный трактат. –2018. –No. 25. –С. 89-91.
2. Meyliyevna B. M. The development of cognitive interests in older Preschoolers in the process of getting acquainted With nature

- //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. –Т. 12. –No.
3. –С. 121-128. 4. Meyliyevna B. M. THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE INTERESTS IN OLDER PRESCHOOLERS IN THE PROCESS OF GETTING ACQUAINTED WITH NATURE.
4. Meyliyevna B. M. The quality of preschool education at the present stage //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. –Т. 11. –No. 10. –С. 2267-2271.
5. Berdiyeva M., Bo‘Ranova S. Maktabgacha va boshlang‘ich ta’limda nutq o‘stirish mashg‘ulotlari orqalibolalarning mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatlarini shakllantirishning samarali usullari //Science and Education. –2021. –Т. 2. –No. 4. –С. 425-429.
6. Бердиева М. М. ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЕ ПРЕДМЕТНОПРОСТРАНСТВЕННОЙ РАЗВИВАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ //Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования. – 2018. –С. 156-159